

Electro Dynamic and Plasmonic Features of Nano-Plasmonic Bow Tie Antenna

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Abstract

Nano-plasmonic bow tie antennas are similar to other antennas except that, it is the size of nano and is specifically designed for very wide bandwidth, theoretically infinite. The electromagnetic system of nano-plasmonic bow tie antenna produces the incident energy that have numerical aperture matched to the far-field beam pattern of the antenna.

This paper discloses electrodynamic and plasmonic features of nano scale bow tie antenna. These nano structures have a vast array of applications due to their ability to focus incident light into a narrow region of extremely high. It also focuses on E-field enhancement intensity between various planes such as Gaussian and continuous source for specific parameters and geometry of the nano-plasmonic bow tie antenna.

Keywords

Nano-Bow Tie Antenna; Antenna; Wideband Antenna

1. Introduction

Bow tie antennas are specified by the angle between two metal pieces. Antenna feed is at the center of the antenna. Antenna should be long in both directions so wavelength never comes in the equation. As a result, bow tie antenna would theoretically have an infinite bandwidth because if its works at one frequency, it supposed to work at all frequencies, because antenna looks the same at all wavelengths [1, 2] (figure1).

Figure: 1 Illustrates Representation of Bow Tie Antenna

Nano bow tie antennas are similar to optical equivalent antennas that can be used to transmit and receive information at microwave and as well as radio frequencies. Many of these applications can be possible because a nano antenna enhances photo physical singularity for instance local electric field [3].

A nano plasmonic antenna is positioned in the path of the in the incident energy beam with a wavelength. It is positioned in the path of the incident energy beam and has at least conductive region which have output ends that are electrically separated by a gap whose lateral dimension is significantly less than wavelength [4].

One of the unique properties of plasmonic structures is it has spontaneous emission rates and internal quantum efficiencies that can be increased by using plasmonic structures [5].

Nano structures are excited by light that can enhance electric field when tuned to plasmonic resonance.

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For further insight into the plasmonic field effect, far field and near field phase matching effects are combined to modulate the harmonic spectral phase towards the emission of single attosecond pulse. For an experiment using bowtie geometry could be interpreted as nearly equal of plasma and harmonic radiation. However, thermal damage of gold nanostructures limits the applicability of the plan. The atoms inside the gap will interact with various inhomogeneous field factors and are subjected to close to the gold bowties and weaker field magnification as the distance from the bowtie gap and edges increases [6].

Control of plasmonic nano antennas was accomplished by Abate, Y. et al. and in that structured nano domains were reversibly transforms infrared plasmonic dipole nano antennas to monopole nano antennas. Primarily, it can be triggered on femtosecond timescale to allow ultrafast nanoscale control of optical occurrences [7].

Surface Plasmon resonance of single bowtie nano-antennas was performed by Kaniber M, et al. using a differential reflectivity method and it had structural and optical properties of individual bowtie nano antennas on glass and semiconductor substrates such as Gas and combination of highly reproducible nanofabrication routes towards future semiconductor based on nano plasmonic circuits involving of multiple photonic and plasmonic entities [8].

The remarkable behavior of light under the effect of Plasmons not only allows super lensing, which can also be a good imaging which can be possible through a uniform thin metal film, that also offer nano imaging of practical trials by using a localized surface Plasmon mode at the angle of a metallic nano probe [9].

2. Nano-Plasmonic Bow Tie Antenna

Nano-plasmonic bow tie antennas are in the nanometer range. Nano-plasmonic has much better bandwidth. In general, antennas with more volume have wider bandwidth. More radiation modes can fit on the structure when the current is less constrained.

To understand electrodynamic and plasmonic features of nano-plasmonic bow tie antenna, simulation was performed for Gaussian pulse and continuous source. Major features such as In Plane: E-field Enhancement (E^2) Intensity, X-Z Plane at $Y=2.0$ nm: E-field Enhancement (E^2) Intensity, X-Z Plane at $X=2.0$ nm: E-field Enhancement (E^2) Intensity, Intensity Plot

at $Z=12.0$ nm: E-field Enhancement (E^2) Intensity (normalized), Enhancement (E^2), Normalized – versus Time, Enhancement (E^2), Normalized – Spectrum versus Frequency, Enhancement (E^2), Normalized – Spectrum versus Wavelength, Complex Dielectric Function for Gold: Real Part – Data and Model vs. Wavelength, Complex Dielectric Function for Gold: Imaginary Part – Data and Model vs. Wavelength has been depicted for Gaussian and continuous source and observations such as Highest intensity, low intensity and no intensity within the timeframe has been documented (figure 2) [10].

Figure: 2 Illustrates Representation of Nano-Plasmonic Bow Tie Antenna

3. ElectroDynamic and Plasmonic Features of Nano-Plasmonic Bow Tie Antenna Using Gaussian Pulse

A simulation was performed for nano-plasmonic bow tie antenna to understand electrodynamics and plasmonic features using Gaussian pulse [11].

A. In Plane: E-field Enhancement (E^2) Intensity (figures 3- 10) (Table 1)

Figure: 3 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity at Time (Femtosec.) =0.801(In Plane)

Figure: 4 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity at Time (Femtosec.) = 4.27 (In Plane)

Figure: 7 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity at Time (Femtosec.) = 11.5 (In Plane)

Figure: 5 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity at Time (Femtosec.) = 6.67 (In Plane)

Figure: 8 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity at Time (Femtosec.) = 12.5 (In Plane)

Figure: 6 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity at Time (Femtosec.) = 7.74 (In Plane)

Figure: 9 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity at Time (Femtosec.) = 15.5 (In Plane)

Figure: 10 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity at Time (Femtosec.) = 22.4 (In Plane)

Figure: 12 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity at Time (Femtosec.) = 1.07 (X-Z Plane at Y=2.0 Nm)

Table: 1 Simulation Notes for Nano-Plasmonic Bow Tie Antenna Using Gaussian Pulse (In Plane: E-Field Enhancement (E^2) Intensity)

SI No:	Simulation Specifications	Values
1	Electric Field Enhancement (Absolute, (V/m) ²)	2.89e+01
2	Electric Field Enhancement (Normalized)	2.31e+02

Figure: 13 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity at Time (Femtosec.) = 3.74 (X-Z Plane at Y=2.0 Nm)

B. Observations of In Plane: E-field Enhancement (E^2) Intensity

1. Highest intensity of In Plane E-field was at Time (femtosec) = 22.4
2. Significant intensity of In Plane E-field was at Time 7.74, 11.5, 12.5, 15.5 and 22.4 (femtosec) for the given parameters
3. Low intensity of In Plane E-field was at Time 4.27, 6.67(femtosec)
4. No intensity of In Plane E-field was at Time 0.801

C. X-Z Plane at Y=2.0 nm: E-field Enhancement (E^2) Intensity (figures 11- 16) (Table 2)

Figure: 11 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity at Time (Femtosec.) = 0.534 (X-Z Plane at Y=2.0 Nm)

Figure: 14 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity at Time (Femtosec.) = 7.74 (X-Z Plane at Y=2.0 Nm)

Figure: 15 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity at Time (Femtosec.) = 11.2 (X-Z Plane at Y=2.0 Nm)

Figure: 16 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity at Time (Femtosec.) = 20.7 (X-Z Plane at Y=2.0 Nm)

Table: 2 Simulation Notes for Nano-Plasmonic Bow Tie Antenna Using Gaussian Pulse (X-Z Plane at Y=2.0 Nm: E-Field Enhancement (E²) Intensity)

SI No:	Simulation Specifications	Values
1	Electric Field Enhancement (Absolute, (V/m) ²)	4.93e+01
2	Electric Field Enhancement (Normalized)	3.95e+02

D. Observations of X-Z Plane at Y=2.0 nm: E-field Enhancement (E²) Intensity

1. Highest intensity of X-Z Plane at Y=2.0 nm: E-field was at Time (femtosec) = 3.74
2. Significant intensity of X-Z Plane at Y=2.0 nm: E-field was at Time 1.07, 3.74, 7.74, 11.2 and 20.07 (femtosec) for

the given parameters

3. Low intensity of X-Z Plane at Y=2.0 nm: E-field was at Time 0.534 (femtosec)

E. X-Z Plane at X=2.0 nm: E-field Enhancement (E²) Intensity (Figure. 17-22) (Table 3)

Figure: 17 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity at Time (Femtosec.) = 1.33 (X-Z Plane at X=2.0 Nm)

Figure: 18 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity at Time (Femtosec.) = 2.94(X-Z Plane at X=2.0 Nm)

Figure: 19 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity at Time (Femtosec.) = 4.27 (X-Z Plane at X=2.0 Nm)

Figure: 20 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity Of E-Field at Time (Femtosec.) = 6.14 (X-Z Plane at X=2.0 Nm)

Figure: 21 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity at Time (Femtosec.) = 8.54 (X-Z Plane at X=2.0 Nm)

Figure: 22 Illustrates Intensity Of E-Field at Time (Femtosec.) = 17.1 (X-Z Plane at X=2.0 Nm)

Table: 3 Simulation Notes for Nano-Plasmonic Bow Tie Antenna Using Gaussian Pulse (X-Z Plane at X=2.0 Nm: E-Field Enhancement (E^2) Intensity)

SI No:	Simulation Specifications	Values
1	Electric Field Enhancement (Absolute, (V/m) ²)	2.71e+01
2	Electric Field Enhancement (Normalized)	2.17e+02

F. Observations of X-Z Plane at X=2.0 nm: E-field Enhancement (E^2) Intensity

1. Highest intensity of X-Z Plane at X=2.0 nm: E-field was at Time (femtosec) = 6.14
2. Significant intensity of X-Z Plane at X=2.0 nm: E-field was at Time 2.94, 4.2 and, 6.14 (femtosec) for the given parameters
3. Low intensity of X-Z Plane at X=2.0 nm: E-field was at Time 8.54 and 17.1 (femtosec)
4. No intensity of X-Z Plane at X=2.0 nm: E-field was at Time 1.33

G. Intensity Plot at Z=12.0 nm: E-field Enhancement (E^2) Intensity (normalized) (Figures 23-29)

Figure: 23 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity (Normalized) at Time (Femtosec.) = 1.6 (Intensity Plot at Z=12.0nm)

Figure: 24 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity (Normalized) at Time (Femtosec.) = 8.81 (Intensity Plot at Z=12.0nm)

Figure: 25 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity (Normalized) at Time (Femtosec.) = 9.87 (Intensity Plot at Z=12.0nm)

Figure: 28 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity (Normalized) of E-Field at Time (Femtosec.) = 11.5 (Intensity Plot at Z=12.0 Nm)

Figure: 26 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity (Normalized) at Time (Femtosec.) = 10.1 (Intensity Plot at Z=12.0nm)

Figure: 29 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity (Normalized) of E-Field at Time (Femtosec.) = 12.5 (Intensity Plot at Z=12.0 Nm)

Figure: 27 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity (Normalized) at Time (Femtosec.) = 11.2 (Intensity Plot at Z=12.0nm)

H. Enhancement (E^2), Normalized – versus Time

Figure: 30 Illustrates Graph for Normalized Versus Time

I. Enhancement (E²), Normalized – Spectrum versus Frequency

Figure: 31 Illustrates Graph for Spectrum versus Time

J. Enhancement (E²), Normalized – Spectrum versus Wavelength

Figure: 32 Illustrates Graph for Spectrum versus Wavelength

K. Complex Dielectric Function for Gold: Real Part – Data and Model vs. Wavelength

Figure: 33 Illustrates Graph for Complex Dielectric Function for Gold Real Part: Data and Model versus Wavelength

L. Complex Dielectric Function for Gold: Imaginary Part – Data and Model vs. Wavelength

Figure: 34 Illustrates Graph for Complex Dielectric Function for Gold Imaginary Part: Data and Model versus Wavelength

Table: 4 Simulation Notes for Nano-Plasmonic Bow Tie Antenna Using Gaussian Pulse (Source Parameters)

SI No:	Source Parameters	Values
1	Source Polarization	X-directional Polarization
2	Amplitude (V/m)	1
3	Central Wavelength (nm)	800
4	Temporal Width (femtosecond)	2
5	Duration of Gaussian Source (Number of Widths)	10

Table: 5 Simulation Notes for Nano-Plasmonic Bow Tie Antenna Using Gaussian Pulse (Structure Parameters)

SI No:	Structure/Material/Substrate/Geometry Parameters	Values
1	Material Dielectric Constant	5
2	Material Dielectric Properties	Gold
3	Triangle Altitude (Geometry)	76
4	Radius of Curvature(Geometry)	12
5	Material Thickness	24
6	Gap Size(Geometry)	16
7	Top SubstrateDielectric Constant	2.2
8	Top Substrate Dielectric Properties	Insulator
9	Top Substrate Thickness	50
10	Bottom SubstrateDielectric Constant	2
11	Bottom Substrate Dielectric Properties	Insulator
12	Bottom Substrate Thickness	50

Table: 6 Simulation Notes for Nano-Plasmonic Bow Tie Antenna Using Gaussian Pulse (Output Parameters)

SI No:	Output Simulation Parameters	Values
1	Z Height of analysis plane	12
2	Output Slices per Optical Cycle	10
3	Output E-field energy density (D*E/2) [Analysis Plane]	No
4	Output electric field enhancement (E^2)[Analysis Plane]	Yes
5	Output E-field components[Analysis Plane]	No
6	Output magnetic field components	No
7	Z height of analysis volume (above substrate surface)	30
8	Z depth of analysis volume (below substrate surface)	10
9	X-Y Width of analysis volume	40
10	Output E-field energy density (D*E/2) [Analysis Volume]	No
11	Output electric field enhancement (E^2)[Analysis Volume]	Yes
12	Output E-field components [Analysis Volume]	Yes
13	Output field components	No
14	Location for spectral analysis within the analysis volume	At points of maximum E-field enhancement (E^2)
15	Output E-field energy density (D*E/2) [Spectral Analysis]	No
16	Output electric field enhancement (E^2)[Spectral Analysis]	Yes
17	Output E-field components[Spectral Analysis]	No
18	Output field components[Spectral Analysis]	No

Table: 7 Simulation Notes for Nano-Plasmonic Bow Tie Antenna Using Gaussian Pulse (Advanced Parameters)

SI No:	Advanced Parameters	Values
1	Courant Factor	0.5
2	Grid Resolution	0.25
3	Simulation Persistence (Optical Cycles, e.g. Central Frequency)	1
4	Cell Size Buffer	40
5	PML Thickness	30
6	Plot Complex Dielectric Functions	Yes

4. ElectroDynamics and Plasmonic Features of Nano-Plasmonic Bow Tie Antenna Using Continuous Source

A simulation was performed for nano-plasmonic bow tie antenna to understand electrodynamics and plasmonic features using Continuous Source [4].

A. In Plane: E-field Enhancement (E^2) Intensity

Figure: 35 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity at Time (Femtosec.) = 1.07 (In Plane)

Figure: 36 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity at Time (Femtosec.) = 2.4 (In Plane)

Figure: 37 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity at Time (Femtosec.) = 3.2 (In Plane)

Figure: 38 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity at Time (Femtosec.) = 13.3 (In Plane)

Table: 8 Simulation Notes for Nano-Plasmonic Bow Tie Antenna Using Continuous Source (In Plane: E-Field Enhancement (E^2) Intensity)

SI No:	Simulation Specifications	Values
1	Electric Field Enhancement (Absolute, $(V/m)^2$)	4.74e+01
2	Electric Field Enhancement (Normalized)	3.79e+02

B. Observations of In Plane: E-field Enhancement (E^2) Intensity

1. Highest intensity of In Plane E-field was at Time (femtosec) = 13.3
2. Significant intensity of In Plane E-field was at Time 1.07, 2.4, 3.2 and 13.3 (femtosec) for the given parameters

C. X-Z Plane at Y=2.0 nm: E-field Enhancement (E^2) Intensity

Figure: 39 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity at Time (Femtosec.) = 1.33 (X-Z Plane at Y=2.0 Nm)

Figure: 40 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity at Time (Femtosec.) = 1.6 (X-Z Plane at Y=2.0 Nm)

Figure: 41 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity at Time (Femtosec.) = 1.87 (X-Z Plane at Y=2.0 Nm)

Figure: 42 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity at Time (Femtosec.) = 4.54 (X-Z Plane at Y=2.0 Nm)

Figure: 43 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity at Time (Femtosec.) = 6.94 (X-Z Plane at Y=2.0 Nm)

Figure: 44 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity at Time (Femtosec.) = 7.47 (X-Z Plane at Y=2.0 Nm)

Figure: 45 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity at Time (Femtosec.) = 23.2 (X-Z Plane at Y=2.0 Nm)

Table: 9 Simulation Notes for Nano-Plasmonic Bow Tie Antenna Using Continuous Source (X-Z Plane at Y=2.0 Nm: E-Field Enhancement (E²) Intensity)

SI No:	Simulation Specifications	Values
1	Electric Field Enhancement (Absolute, (V/m) ²)	7.34e+01
2	Electric Field Enhancement (Normalized)	5.88e+02

D. Observations of X-Z Plane at Y=2.0 nm: E-field Enhancement (E²) Intensity

1. Highest intensity of X-Z Plane at Y=2.0 nm: E-field was at Time (femtosec) = 7.47
2. Significant intensity of X-Z Plane at Y=2.0 nm: E-field was at Time 1.87, 4.54, 6.94, 7.47, 23.2 (femtosec) for the given parameters
3. Very Low intensity of X-Z Plane at Y=2.0 nm: E-field was at Time 1.6 (femtosec)
4. No intensity of X-Z Plane at Y=2.0 nm: E-field was at Time 1.33 (femtosec)

E. X-Z Plane at X=2.0 nm: E-field Enhancement (E²) Intensity

Figure: 46. Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity at Time (Femtosec.) = 0.534 (X-Z Plane at X=2.0 Nm)

Figure: 47 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity at Time (Femtosec.) = 0.801 (X-Z Plane at X=2.0 Nm)

Figure: 48 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity at Time (Femtosec.) = 1.33 (X-Z Plane at X=2.0 Nm)

Figure: 49 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity at Time (Femtosec.) = 13.3 (X-Z Plane at X=2.0 Nm)

Figure: 50 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity at Time (Femtosec.) = 21.9 (X-Z Plane at X=2.0 Nm)

Table: 10 Simulation Notes for Nano-Plasmonic Bow Tie Antenna Using Continuous Source (X-Z Plane at X=2.0 Nm: E-Field Enhancement (E²) Intensity)

SI No:	Simulation Specifications	Values
1	Electric Field Enhancement (Absolute, (V/m) ^2)	4.14e+01
2	Electric Field Enhancement (Normalized)	3.31e+02

F. Observations of X-Z Plane at X=2.0 nm: E-field Enhancement (E²) Intensity

1. Highest intensity of X-Z Plane at X=2.0 nm: E-field was at Time (femtosec) = 13.3
2. Significant intensity of X-Z Plane at X=2.0 nm: E-field was at Time 0.801, 1.33, 13.3 and 21.9 (femtosec) for the given parameters
3. Low intensity of X-Z Plane at X=2.0 nm: E-field was at Time 0.534 (femtosec)

G. Intensity Plot at Z=12.0 nm: E-field Enhancement (E²) Intensity (normalized)

Figure: 51 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity (Normalized) at Time (Femtosec.) = 1.6 (Intensity Plot at Z=12.0nm)

Figure: 52 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity (Normalized) at Time (Femtosec.) = 1.87 (Intensity Plot at Z=12.0nm)

Figure: 55 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity (Normalized) at Time (Femtosec.) = 4.0 (Intensity Plot at Z=12.0nm)

Figure: 53 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity (Normalized) at Time (Femtosec.) = 2.67 (Intensity Plot at Z=12.0nm)

Figure: 56 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity (Normalized) at Time (Femtosec.) = 5.34 (Intensity Plot at Z=12.0nm)

Figure: 54 Illustrates E-Field Enhancement Intensity (Normalized) at Time (Femtosec.) = 3.74 (Intensity Plot at Z=12.0nm)

H. Enhancement (E^2), Normalized – versus Time

Figure: 57 Illustrates Graph for Normalized versus Time

I. Enhancement (E²), Normalized – Spectrum versus Frequency

Figure: 58 Illustrates Graph for Normalized – Spectrum versus Frequency

J. Enhancement (E²), Normalized – Spectrum versus Wavelength

Figure: 59 Illustrates Graph for Normalized – Spectrum versus Wavelength

K. Complex Dielectric Function for Gold: Real Part – Data and Model vs. Wavelength

Figure: 60 Illustrates Graph for Complex Dielectric Function for Gold: Real Part – Data and Model versus Wavelength

L. Complex Dielectric Function for Gold: Imaginary Part – Data and Model vs. Wavelength

Figure: 61 Illustrates Graph for Complex Dielectric Function for Gold: Imaginary Part – Data and Model versus Wavelength

Table: 11 Simulation Notes for Nano-Plasmonic Bow Tie Antenna Using Continuous Source (Source Parameters)

SI No:	Source Parameters	Values
1	Source Polarization	X-directional Polarization
2	Amplitude (V/m)	1
3	Wavelength (nm)	800
4	Temporal Width (femtosecond)	2
5	End Time for Continuous Source (Optical Cycles)	10

Table: 12 Simulation Notes for Nano-Plasmonic Bow Tie Antenna Using Continuous Source (Structure Parameters)

SI No:	Structure/Material/Substrate/Geometry Parameters	Values
1	Material Dielectric Constant	5
2	Material Dielectric Properties	Gold
3	Triangle Altitude (Geometry)	76
4	Radius of Curvature (Geometry)	12
5	Material Thickness	24
6	Gap Size (Geometry)	16
7	Top Substrate Dielectric Constant	2.2
8	Top Substrate Dielectric Properties	Insulator
9	Top Substrate Thickness	50
10	Bottom Substrate Dielectric Constant	2
11	Bottom Substrate Dielectric Properties	Insulator
12	Bottom Substrate Thickness	50

Table: 13 Simulation Notes for Nano-Plasmonic Bow Tie Antenna Using Continuous Source (Output Parameters)

SI No:	Output Simulation Parameters	Values
1	Z Height of analysis plane	12
2	Output Slices per Optical Cycle	10
3	Output E-field energy density (D*E/2) [Analysis Plane]	No
4	Output electric field enhancement (E^2) [Analysis Plane]	Yes
5	Output E-field components [Analysis Plane]	No
6	Output magnetic field components	No
7	Z height of analysis volume (above substrate surface)	30
8	Z depth of analysis volume (below substrate surface)	10
9	X-Y Width of analysis volume	40
10	Output E-field energy density (D*E/2) [Analysis Volume]	No
11	Output electric field enhancement (E^2) [Analysis Volume]	Yes
12	Output E-field components [Analysis Volume]	No
13	Output field components	No
14	Location for spectral analysis within the analysis volume	At points of maximum E-field enhancement (E^2)
15	Output E-field energy density (D*E/2) [Spectral Analysis]	No
16	Output electric field enhancement (E^2) [Spectral Analysis]	Yes
17	Output E-field components [Spectral Analysis]	No
18	Output field components [Spectral Analysis]	No

Table: 14 Simulation Notes for Nano-Plasmonic Bow Tie Antenna Using Continuous Source (Advanced Parameters)

SI No:	Advanced Parameters	Values
1	Courant Factor	0.5
2	Grid Resolution	0.25
3	Simulation Persistence (Optical Cycles, e.g. Central Frequency)	1
4	Cell Size Buffer	40
5	PML Thickness	30
6	Plot Complex Dielectric Functions	Yes

5. Results

From the above observations and illustrations for nano-plasmonic bowtie antenna:

1. Simulation was performed for Gaussian Pulse and Continuous Source
2. Illustrations are plotted and documented
3. All parameters such as source, structure, output and advanced are documented
4. Electrodynamics and plasmonic features of Bowtie antenna has been studied for the specific parameters

6. Simulation Results for Gaussian Pulse

1. Highest intensity of In Plane E-field was at Time (femtosec) = 22.4
2. Highest intensity of X-Z Plane at Y=2.0 nm: E-field was at Time (femtosec) = 3.74
3. Highest intensity of X-Z Plane at X=2.0 nm: E-field was at Time (femtosec) = 6.14
4. Highest E-field Enhancement Intensity (normalized) of E-field at Time (femtosec.) = 11.5 (Intensity Plot at Z=12.0 nm)
5. Plotted graph for Enhancement (E^2), Normalized – versus Time
6. Plotted graph for Enhancement (E^2), Normalized – Spectrum versus Frequency
7. Plotted graph for Enhancement (E^2), Normalized – Spectrum versus Wavelength
8. Plotted graph for Complex Dielectric Function for Gold: Real and Imaginary Part – Data and Model vs. Wavelength

7. Simulation Results for Continuous Source

1. Highest intensity of In Plane E-field was at Time (femtosec) = 13.3

2. Highest intensity of X-Z Plane at Y=2.0 nm: E-field was at Time (femtosec) = 7.47
3. Highest intensity of X-Z Plane at X=2.0 nm: E-field was at Time (femtosec) = 13.3
4. Highest E-field Enhancement Intensity (normalized) at Time (femtosec.) = 5.34 (Intensity Plot at Z=12.0 nm)
5. Plotted graph for Enhancement (E^2), Normalized – versus Time
6. Plotted graph for Enhancement (E^2), Normalized – Spectrum versus Frequency
7. Plotted graph for Enhancement (E^2), Normalized – Spectrum versus Wavelength
8. Plotted graph for Complex Dielectric Function for Gold: Real and Imaginary Part – Data and Model vs. Wavelength

8. Conclusion

In this review paper Electric field of nano plasmonic bow tie antenna is illustrated and analysis of Electric field intensity is depicted with graphs representing highest, lowest, and no radiation pattern of nano plasmonic bow tie antenna in femtosecond for Gaussian pulse, continuous source and simulation characteristics are documented in the tables.

In comparison with other papers, this review paper discusses more about intensity of electric field in various planes in femtoseconds.

9. Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts of interest as per author's point of view.

10. Appendix

1. Gaussian Pulse

It is the wave packet (Gaussian- distributed frequency) of a specified with incident on the antenna at $t=0$.

2. Continuous Source

It produces a monochromatic plane wave incident on the antenna at $t=0$

3. Material Properties

Using material properties will accurately replicate the material's optical behavior in the simulation

4. Bowtie Geometry

The bowtie antenna to be simulated is formed from two opposed equilateral triangular gold nano-particles

separated by a gap.

5. Substrate Properties

The top substrate is the dielectric layer directly the bowtie antenna. The bottom substrate is the dielectric layer beneath the top substrate layer.

6. Planar Outputs

An X-Y planar cut through the simulation cell at a height above the substrate surface. Output will consist of sequences of field value distribution.

7. Volume Outputs

A 3-D volume centered in the bowtie gap with field distribution sequences in an X-Z planar cut through the center and field distribution sequences in a Y-Z planar cut through the center.

8. Spectral Outputs

Graphical plots of field distributions versus time, frequency and wavelength at a point.

9. Resolution

It determines the size of the characteristic simulation pixel of space. The larger it is, the better the special resolution. Increasing the resolution could potentially lead to more realistic simulation results.

10. Courant factor

It determines the size of the characteristic simulation time step. The smaller it is, the better the time resolution. For more purposes 0.5 is sufficient.

11. Simulation Persistence

It determines how long simulation runs after the source turns off. This can be a useful feature for extending the simulation time in order to view field decay and measure the antenna quality factor Q

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